

TEACHING LINGUISTIC DISCIPLINES AT THE LANGUAGE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: The article deals with the problems of teaching theory academic disciplines such as general linguistics, theoretical grammatics, lexicology, translation theory, stylistics and interpretation of the text in the light of new trends in linguistics. Put forward and substantiated by the assumption that, under the influence of such disciplines as communicative linguistics, pragmalinguistics, cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology university programs in the theory of language should be essential but updated and expanded.

Key words: communicative, cognitive, pragmatic, culture, foreign language, lecture courses, translation theory.

Introduction:

As you know, teaching a foreign language as a secondary language involves gaining not only practical knowledge, but also a deep knowledge of the theory of the language. However, today, teaching theoretical disciplines is not fully complied with modern requirements. First of all, insufficient consideration of modern trends in linguistics research is causing to decrease the quality of education. In particular, the achievements of teaching students in these methods are obtained in the sphere of linguistics, cognitive linguistics, linguistic pragmatics, linguoculturology and intercultural communication.

As it is known that, the heart of the communicative approach is the striving to the study of the language in its real functioning, in the conditions of a specific communication situation in accordance with the goals communicants. The

communicative approach which considers a functioning language as a dynamic of the activity process penetrates into all levels of the language system, which is quite natural, as it contributes to more complete coverage of the essence of the phenomenon under study. Analysis of linguistic units in the context of their specific implementation and taking into account all possible parameters and conditions of a certain situation communication allows you to get the most complete objective information formation of both the semantic content of these units, and about the laws of their functioning. Orientation to communication has put forward a number of serious theoretical problems and required a revision many traditional concepts of the apparatus itself and methods of linguistic description of the language. The concepts of communicative act and discourse, and related categories of addressee and addresser, emphasizes the role of extralinguistic facts which determines language communication. In this regard, in all lecture courses on linguistics, theoretical grammar math, lexicology, stylistics, etc. need an introduction sections, including issues related to communicative the essence of a linguistic unit (lexemes, phrases, phrases, zeological unit, text), its communicative functions taking into account all stages of the use of a verbal sign: selection, functioning, impact and perception. For example,, in the course of lexicology it is advisable to consider questions communicative-semantic potential of words, communication model of lexical meaning, the concept of actual meaning of the word, which is understood as the totality of communication creatively relevant themes in a particular communicative act. In my opinion, much attention in lecture courses is necessary and it should be given to the pragmatic aspects of the language, as one of the directions of communicative linguistics. Linguo-pragmatic is defined as a science that studies the relations between the language and those who use it. In the field of study issues of linguopragmatics include: the study of speech acts and contexts of their implementation, aspect of functioning language units, the choice of which is determined by the intentionally, influencing tasks of the sender of the text, successfulness and effectiveness of communication, speech interpretation listener, the attitude of the addressee to the content of the statement, development of conventions

and rules governing the processes of language communication and many others. Other areas closely related to cognitive linguistics and they are called linguoculturology and intercultural communication. We know that language is part of culture. Studies show that learning foreign languages outside the context of culture is unjustified and impossible.

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